

Approaching Exascale with the Weather Research and Forecasting Solar Model

Jacob Finkenrath^{a,*}, Giannis Koutsou^a, Swen Metzger^a, Hendrik Elbern^{b,c}, Jonas Berndt^b

^aComputation-based Science and Technology Research Center, The Cyprus Institute, 20 Kavafi Str., Nicosia 2121, Cyprus

^bInstitute für Energie und Klimaforschung, Forschungszentrum Jülich, Wilhelm-Johnen-Strae, 52428 Jülich

^cRheinisches Institute für Umweltforschung, University of Cologne, Albertus-Magnus-Platz 50923 Köln

Abstract

We investigate the scalability and I/O performance of the Weather Research Forecasting (WRF) model on the PRACE Tier-0 systems SuperMUC-Haswell, Marconi KNL, and Marenostrum 4 within the PRACE 5th Implementation phase in cooperation with the Energy Oriented Centre of Excellence (EoCoE). We identify the bottlenecks which can impede WRF to run efficiently on pre-exascale and exascale machines. We report on the performance of both the computational kernels and I/O as captured using *Scalasca/Score-P* and *extrae*. From a series of strong scaling tests and benchmarks in which we vary the parallelization using different MPI and OpenMP setups, we identify strategies to run efficiently on PRACE Tier-0 machines. The analysis is carried out for three schemes, namely the weather forecast scheme, the scheme based on WRFsolar, and the WRF-fire scheme.

1. Introduction

As we approach exascale, there is a pressing need to optimize scientific application codes to be ready to scale efficiently to millions of processes. A particular challenge in this case is optimizing data movement and access to I/O. The Weather Research and Forecast model (WRF) [1] is particularly demanding on I/O, typically requiring a series of pre- and post-processing steps during which data may be read and/or written to storage. Enabling WRF on exascale therefore necessitates first addressing the I/O bottleneck.

This whitepaper reports on an analysis of the I/O performance of WRF on current PRACE Tier-0 supercomputers, with an outlook on exascale. The project enables activities within PRACE 5IP and the Energy Oriented Centre of Excellence (EoCoE). It includes an identification of functions with high work-loads and an analysis of I/O and data management in order to understand bottlenecks of applications of WRF on exascale systems.

The specific model investigated here is based on the solar branch of WRF (WRFsolar) [2]. WRFsolar is an augmentation of WRF in terms of improved irradiance forecasts for solar power predictions. This includes in particular the computation of diagnostic variables related to the energy sector as well as improved representations of cloud-aerosol interactions, aerosol-feedback and cloud-feedback. Predictions of such processes are necessary for more accurate estimates of solar power from Photovoltaic Cells (PVCs) and solar-thermal plants, which become increasingly important in the energy sector to (i) facilitate a stable electrical grid and (ii) realize a cost-optimized integration of solar power through energy stock exchange. Beyond WRFsolar, this whitepaper looks into related test-cases, such as the standard weather forecast scheme and WRF-fire.

The whitepaper is structured as follows: in section 2. we present the PRACE Tier-0 systems used in this analysis, in section 3. we discuss some important features of the WRF software package and the physical models which have been used, in section 4. we detail the strategy employed to identify a test case appropriate for use with the performance analysis packages we employed, which we then use in section 5. to perform different scaling tests. In section 6. we compare the performance across PRACE Tier-0 systems identifying bottlenecks specific to the underlying machine and identifying opportunities for optimization. In section 7. we report results obtained when using a hybrid parallelization approaching with MPI and OpenMP and in section 8. we test different I/O strategies, namely using *parallel NetCDF*. In section 9. we comment on the case of the performance on Intel Knights Landing (KNL) architectures and in section 10. we discuss the WRF-fire branch. We conclude with a discussion about the status of WRF and its readiness for exascale computing in section 11.

* Corresponding author e-mail: j.finkenrath@cyi.ac.cy, telephone: +357 222 08 606

2. Machines

For the analysis that will follow we identified a set of PRACE Tier-0 machines that employed different architectures, so as to obtain the WRF performance results on as many different HPC environments as possible. To this end, for the analysis on CPU based systems we used Marenostrum 4 and SuperMUC, while for analysis using Xeon Phi accelerators we ran on Marconi’s KNL partition. Marenostrum 4 at BSC is equipped with nodes equipped with two Intel Skylake CPUs with 24 cores each. The nodes are connected via a 100 Gb Intel OmniPath Full-Fat Tree Communication network. The SuperMUC Haswell partition at LRZ is equipped with a Lenovo NeXtScale system where each node hosts two 14-core Intel Haswell CPUs. The nodes are connected via Infiniband FDR14. The Marconi KNL partition at CINECA is equipped with nodes consisting of one Intel Xeon Phi 7250 “KNL”, connected via an Intel OmniPath Network. All three HPC systems use GPFS as their parallel filesystem. We note that during the runs for this analysis, the clock frequency of the Haswell CPUs on SuperMUC was set to a maximum of 1.8 GHz. We will identify results that were obtained after this change when presenting the data.

3. WRF setup

For our analysis we employ the most recent version of WRF, WRF 4.0, released in 06/2018 [1]. WRF 4.0 is parallelized using domain decomposition techniques, where communication between domains are done via *MPI*. Moreover local computation in each domain can be parallelized using *OpenMP*. Since version 4.0, WRF uses the library NetCDF by default for writing files. Using the tools *Scalasca/Score-P*, we identified a set of test cases that on one hand were sufficiently close to realistic workloads while on the other hand allowed for parallelization from small to medium sized partitions with reasonable turnover of jobs. Namely, we used grid-sizes which include volumes from $V = 192^2 \times 50$ to $V = 1536^2 \times 50$ which have output file from 300 MB to 2.2 GB. Runs were carried out for three branches of WRF, namely the scheme used for weather forecasting, which we refer to as **(model 1)**, the scheme which can be used for irradiance forecasts, which we refer to as **(model 2)**, and a scheme for fire forecasting, which we refer to as **(model 3)**. For completeness, we include in appendices B1., B2., and B3. the parameters used for each of the three models respectively.

For model 1 we use the Morrison double-moment scheme (`mp_physics=10`) in combination with the RRTMG (Rapid Radiative Transfer Model) scheme for long- and shortwave radiation (`ra_lw(sw)_physics=4`). For model 2 we use WRF Single-Moment 5-class scheme (`mp_physics=4`) in combination with the rapid radiative transfer scheme for long (`ra_sw_physics=1`) and the Goddard shortwave scheme for shortwave radiation (`ra_sw_physics=2`). For model 3, the fire forecast, we use parameters which are provided by the test case of WRF 4.0 which are the default ones where the microphysics and long- and short radiations are not taken into account (`mp_physics=0` and `ra_lw(sw)_physics=0`).

The integration is done by a Runge Kutta scheme of order 3. The integration step sizes are chosen with respect to the resolution of the physical box. A rule of thumb is to set a step size in seconds as 3 times the resolution in km, e.g. for the case of a resolution of 80 km, an integration step size of less than or equal to 4 minutes is recommended. Thus, if the global physical box size is kept constant, by increasing the resolution the computational effort per simulation increases by the number of grid points times the number of integration steps. In our scaling test, we will average the time to solution or time to write over all applied steps. When presenting the data and explaining the bottlenecks, it is useful to keep in mind that the computational kernel, i.e. the integration step, requires from tens of ms to a few seconds per call, while I/O occurs about once per hour of simulation time, and requires between a few seconds to hundreds of seconds.

4. Analysis of the Computational and I/O kernels

First we use *Scalasca/Score-P* to analyze WRF. We choose a relatively small volume of $V = 65 \times 45 \times 30$ and an older version of WRF, namely WRF 3.6, due to the fact that WRF 4 was not released at the time of this analysis. With WRF 3.6 we could use MPI to scale up to 540 parallel tasks. This results in a local volume size per MPI process of $V_{local} \geq 10^2 \times L_z$ which is smaller than the minimum possible in WRF 4. Using WRF 3.6, we could scale to even smaller lattice sizes which enables us to shed light on possible bottlenecks in case of massive parallelization. Note that this bound of parallelization can be further extended by using a hybrid parallelization scheme using multiple OpenMP threads per MPI task. We will discuss this in detail in the section 7..

We start our analysis using *Scalasca/Score-P* on SuperMUC and *extrae* on Marenostrum. A simulation run using model 1 can be divided in 3 major subtasks: the initialization, the integration, and the finalization. During initialization, the input parameters and input data are read in by rank 0. The parameters are then distributed via `MPI_Bcast` while the input data via `MPI_Scatter`. For our test volume case, the time for the initialization phase was minor compare to the integration phase, which includes writing of the simulation data to disk. Moreover, also in the case of our largest test case, the input sizes used were relatively moderate at 2.2 GB. The time for reading the inputs was therefore minor compare to the total run time and was not identified as a bottleneck to the total run time.

The most significant part of the run time is in the integration routine, given by the function `module_integrate`, as illustrated by Fig. 1, where the total run time is given by *Total*. The function `module_integrate` consists of three major parts, functions which are involved in I/O before and after integration (`med_before_solve_io`

Fig. 1. Execution time in seconds of the main integration routine as a function of the number of MPI processes. Results were obtained using *Scalasca/Score-P* and a global volume of $V = 64 \times 45 \times 30$. The total runtime is shown using the circles and the different parts are shown with the squares, plus signs, crosses, and triangles as indicated in the legend.

and `med_last_solve_io`) and the computational kernel (`solve_interface`). We show the scaling of the different components in Fig. 1 on the Haswell partition of SuperMUC on up to 19 nodes which corresponds to 540 MPI tasks. As indicated by the figure, the computational kernel, namely `module_integrate`, scales well to a parallelization of around 100 MPI tasks which corresponds to a local volume with around 780 grid points. Moreover, for around 200 MPI tasks we find a reasonable speed-up, which corresponds to a local domain consisting of around 400 grid points. The scaling is mainly hindered by communications of the boundary terms. This communication is done via the non-blocking MPI routines (`MPI_Isend`, `MPI_Irecv`, `MPI_Wait`). By taking a closer look via *extrae*, the communication only hinders slightly the overall performance if the local volume is larger than 700 grid points. For smaller local volumes, thus larger parallelization, the time to solution of the computational kernel flattens out.

The timing of I/O routines are stable up to around 65 MPI tasks. For larger parallelizations, of around 200 MPI tasks, the time for I/O increases, becoming larger than the time to solution of the computational kernel. Moreover, for even higher parallelization the I/O dominates the run time for our test cases. To conclude, the I/O and computational kernels are balanced for less than 100 MPI tasks for the selected test case. The reason is that the frequency of the I/O is much lower than the integration steps in a real simulation. For our test case, the time scale of the integration step is given by 4 minutes, while the time scale of I/O is given by 1 hours.

5. Basic strong and weak scaling tests

In this section we discuss the strong and weak scaling tests on Marenostrum 4 and SuperMUC in order to analyze the performance and to point out bottlenecks of the different models. We perform strong scaling tests using parallelization via *MPI* on up to 172 nodes. We summarize the results using model 1 in Tab. 5. for the test case with $V = 384^2 \times 50$. As expected from the previous section, the computational kernel scales well, which is not the case for I/O. On SuperMUC, we found a factor of up to 6 of faster write times compared to Marenostrum 4. Reading of the input is similar on both machines and constant relative to the number of processes.

In the left panel of Fig. 2 we show the strong scaling of the computational kernel of the four different test sizes between $V = 192^2 \times 50$ and $V = 1536^2 \times 50$ on Marenostrum. For larger parallelization, for the chosen problem sizes, the computational kernel time approaches 10 ms, which makes it difficult to measure it reliable and accurate. In the right panel of Fig. 2 we show I/O, where we observe the timing per write to increase proportionally with the size of the grid, but mostly independently of the parallelization.

Although the time scale of integration is given in minutes, while for I/O it is given in hours, for our test cases, the I/O becomes significant for larger test sizes and larger partitions as shown in Fig. 3. For the scaling runs, we perform a physical simulation length of 6 hours, writing out data once per hour, resulting in 7 writes over the total simulation length. The number of integration steps are given by 540 for the smallest test size and 4320 steps for the largest. As can be seen from the Fig. 3, for parallelization over more than 500 MPI tasks, the I/O dominates and uses up to 80% of the runtime in the case of Marenostrum 4. In case of SuperMUC, the

Marenostrum 4				SuperMUC HW			
np	Int-step [s]	write [s]	input [s]	np	Int-step [s]	write [s]	input [s]
96	0.47	12.06	5.22	96	0.74	2.29	6.24
192	0.23	12.07	4.94	192	0.40	2.74	6.20
288	0.15	12.21	4.86	288	0.29	3.10	6.50
480	0.11	39.81	5.02	480	0.19	4.02	6.82
672	0.079	32.37	5.14	672	0.15	5.12	6.45
960	0.0668	25.23	5.09	960	0.12	5.17	7.09

Table 1. Timings for model 1 using a volume of $V = 384^2 \times 50$ ranging from 96 MPI processes (np) to 960 np. Results are shown for Marenostrum 4 (left) and SuperMUC Haswell (right). We show the runtime of the integration kernel (Int-step), for writing the final data to disk (write), and for reading the input parameters (input) in seconds.

Fig. 2. Strong scaling behavior of model 1 on Marenostrum 4 using global volume sizes $V = 192^2 \times 50$ (crosses), $V = 384^2 \times 50$ (triangles), $V = 786^2 \times 50$ (squares), and $V = 1536^2 \times 50$ (stars). In the left panel, we show the strong scaling of the computational kernel, while in the right panel, the strong scaling of the I/O (write).

I/O is not as dominant, however it still increases for larger parallelizations, as shown in Tab. 5.. Due to that, we consider I/O as the main bottleneck for scaling to massive parallelizations, at least for the default case of WRF 4.0 using NetCDF.

As noted, from the right panel of Fig. 2, we see that the I/O time is mostly constant with respect to the number of processes for a given global volume. An exception is the case of $V = 384^2 \times 50$, for which the time for I/O increases for parallelizations larger than 400 processes. We investigate this using *extrae*. We depict in Fig. 4 the output from *extrae* showing calls to I/O for the last 1% of the run time for three parallelizations: 288 MPI tasks, 480 MPI tasks, and 960 MPI tasks, ordered from top to bottom. 1% of the run time corresponds to the final 2.7 secs for the 288 MPI tasks run, 4.8 secs for the 480 MPI tasks run, and 2.8 secs for the 960 MPI tasks run. From the 480 MPI tasks run, we see that the I/O slows down the run time significantly while the computational kernel scales well. As listed in Tab. 5., the time for writing is larger than the depicted section of the run, thus in Fig. 4 the ending of final writing kernel and the finalization of the run is shown. Thus we can directly compare the behavior of the I/O routines. The routine consists of a sequence of an MPI collective functions followed by a write out function performed by rank 0. The write is shown as white points in the figure, while the red color corresponds to minor writing events. However, they are correlated to the calls to MPI functions. Using scalasca, we can identify that this is the point where the data are collected by using `MPI_Gather`. If we now compare the duration of the writes for the different cases, we can conclude that it is not the direct write that causes the slowdown when going from 288 to 480 MPI tasks, but the collective MPI function. This behavior was observed only for the volume of $V = 384^2 \times 50$ on Marenostrum. A natural way to mitigate this bottleneck would be to implement parallel I/O, that would obviate the need for the collective operation.

We study the weak scaling of WRF on Marenostrum 4, shown in Fig. 5, keeping the problem size per process fixed while varying the number of processes. We carry out the weak scaling using local volume sizes between $V_{local} = 7680$ and $V_{local} = 153600$ points. The integration step scales weakly very well. For the chosen sizes we do not see any increase in run time up to parallelizations of around 4000 MPI tasks for the smallest local volume. The I/O, on the other hand, depends on the global volume and therefore increases linearly with the number of processes. This shows again that I/O will dominate runtime on larger partition sizes, similarly to what was

Fig. 3. Ratio of time spent in I/O over total runtime versus the number of processes. We show model 1 on Marenostrom 4 with the global volume kept fixed (strong scaling) for four global volume sizes following the notation of Fig. 2.

Fig. 4. Output of *extrae* when analyzing model 1 with 288 MPI tasks (top), 480 MPI tasks (middle), and 960 MPI tasks (bottom) on Marenostrom, using the problem size $V = 384^2 \times 50$. The figure shows the last 1% of the runtime. White points show the main writing of results, carried out by rank 0, while read dots indicate minor I/O events.

Fig. 5. Weak scaling of model 1 on Marenostrum 4. We show results obtained with local problem sizes: $V_l = 154K$ points (right-pointing triangles), $V_l = 61K$ points (left-pointing triangles), $V_l = 31K$ points (crosses), $V_l = 15K$ points (squares), and $V_l = 8K$ points (stars). In the left panel we show the weak scaling of the computational kernel and in the right panel we show the weak scaling of the writing out of data in seconds.

Table 2. Timings for model 2, using a global volume of $V = 384^2 \times 50$, left for Marenostrum 4 and right for SuperMUC Haswell. The notation is the same as in Tab. 2.

Marenostrum 4				SuperMUC HW			
np	Int-step [s]	write [s]	input [s]	np	Int-step [s]	write [s]	input [s]
96	0.44	10.72	4.25	96	0.52	1.83	5.02
192	0.26	9.29	4.45	192	0.29	2.27	5.23
288	0.24	10.84	4.35	288	0.22	2.63	5.46
480	0.22	32.88	4.15	480	0.16	3.44	5.09
672	0.068	29.18	4.18	672	0.11	4.38	5.43
960	0.064	22.61	4.20	960	0.09	4.63	6.07

concluded after the strong scaling analysis. As pointed out, this is largely due to the collective communication routines used by NetCDF to collect the data and to write them out using a single MPI task, which should be possible to mitigate with the use of parallel I/O.

6. Comparison of machines

As an interesting bi-product of this analysis, we can compare the performance of WRF on two Tier-0 PRACE machines, namely Marenostrum 4 and SuperMUC with reduced frequency. We run models 1 and 2 and compare strong scaling using the test size with $V = 384^2 \times 50$, shown in the left panel of Fig. 6 and in Tab. 5. for model 1 and in the right panel of Fig. 6 and Tab. 2 for model 2. As can be seen from the left panel of Fig. 6, we find WRF performs about 1.7 faster on Marenostrum Skylake CPUs compared to SuperMUC Haswell CPUs. This is not the case for model 2, where the differences are minor. This can be improved if the computational kernel is further optimized to enable AVX512 instructions to use the full potential of Skylake CPUs.

7. Hybrid parallelization approach

We vary the number of OpenMP threads per MPI process to investigate the optimal parallelization strategy. To test different hybrid parallelization setups, we run using 2 nodes of Marenostrum 4, employing model 1 with a volume of $V = 192^2 \times 50$. We list the results in Tab. 3. We find that 8 MPI tasks with 3 OpenMP threads yields the best I/O performance while using 12 MPI tasks with 4 OpenMP threads yields the best computational performance.

To further optimize the performance, we investigate pinning the OpenMP threads and/or MPI threads to the CPUs, however we found that the default setup yields the best results. Thus, we use the following slurm options:

- #SBATCH --cpus-per-task=6
- #SBATCH --tasks-per-node=8

Fig. 6. Comparison of strong scaling of the computational kernels on Marenostrum 4 (crosses) and SuperMUC Haswell (squares) using $V = 384^2 \times 50$. The right panel shows the scaling using model 1 while the left panel shows the scaling using model 2.

Table 3. Performance results on two nodes of Marenostrum 4 using model 1 and a lattice size of $V = 192^2 \times 50$ when varying the number of OpenMP threads per MPI process.

MPI tasks	OpenMP threads	CPU pinned to task	Int-step [s]	write [s]	input [s]
48	1	1	0.156047	3.14105	1.70448
12	4	4	0.142483	2.99587	1.27459
8	6	6	0.149954	3.00015	1.29456
8	3	6	0.148462	2.96947	1.26013

to achieve an optimized hybrid parallelization.

Using the test case with $V = 192^2 \times 50$ we perform a strong scaling test employing the hybrid parallelization on up to 32 nodes. The result is shown in Fig. 7. As already found in section 5., the scaling of model 1 is not ideal for small volumes, as can be seen in the left panel of Fig. 7. Although the time-to-solution decreases with increasing number of processes, the speed-up saturates. This trend persists when hybrid parallelization is used to scale up to 16 nodes. On the right panel of Fig. 7, we show the time per I/O. As already discussed, the I/O stays constant as we increase the number of processes when using the smallest test case. We found the time per write decreases slightly if a hybrid parallelization is used. Although this does not have large impact in the run time for our test case, this could be an approach for larger problem sizes on larger machine partitions.

Note that by using an hybrid parallelization one can scale to a larger number of nodes because the local volume per MPI task is reached on a larger number of nodes.

Moreover, we studied the strong scaling using the hybrid parallelization of the computational kernel by using a larger test size of $V = 384^2 \times 50$. The time-to-solution of the computational kernel is shown in the left panel of Fig. 8. The Hybrid parallelization scales up to 32 nodes, which corresponds to a local volume of 23,000 grid points per node. This means that using hybrid parallelization, WRF 4.0 can scale to a larger number of CPUs than is possible using pure MPI due implemented bound on the minimal local volume per MPI process.

8. Analysis of the I/O

As discussed in section 5., the timing for I/O can become a very significant part of the total run time for larger parallelizations. In the default setup of WRF 4, the I/O is done by using NetCDF. On SuperMUC we used version 4.3 while on Marenostrum we employed version 4.4. The I/O is then done by the MPI task with rank 0. In the I/O procedure, `MPI_Gather` is used to gather the data on rank 0. This turns out to be a scalability bottleneck, inhibiting parallelization on larger partitions.

A solution to this problem may be to use parallel I/O. In WRF 4.0, this can be enabled by using parallel NetCDF. We study the behavior on Marenostrum using strong scaling employing model 1 with a volume of $V = 384^2 \times 50$ for native MPI and hybrid parallelization. The scaling is shown in Fig. 8. The left panel of Fig. 8 shows a comparison of the time to write in three scenarios: i) using NetCDF with MPI, ii) using parallel

Fig. 7. Strong scaling when using only MPI (squares) and when using 3 OpenMP threads per MPI (crosses) for model 1 and $V = 192^2 \times 50$ on up to 32 Marenostrum 4 nodes. The left panel shows time-to-solution of the computational kernel while the right panel shows the time for I/O.

Fig. 8. Strong scaling using parallel NetCDF and Hybrid Parallelization using model 1 with a volume of $V = 384^2 \times 50$. In the left panel we show strong scaling of the computational kernel while in the right panel the strong scaling of the I/O is shown. We compare using NetCDF (crosses), to using parallel NetCDF (squares), and to using parallel NetCDF with hybrid parallelization (stars).

NetCDF with MPI, and iii) using parallel NetCDF with hybrid parallelization. Using parallel NetCDF reduces the time for I/O by an order of magnitude. However, in this case, a reduction of the time by increasing the number of MPI tasks is not observed. However, we found that the time of I/O can be further decreased by using a hybrid parallelization. As shown in the right panel of Fig. 8, the time for I/O reduces for increasing number of nodes. A possible reason for that is that the number of MPI task per node is reduced in the Hybrid setup yielding a more efficient parallel I/O. This shows that approaching massive parallelization, WRF with parallel NetCDF is the most promising setup. To conclude, if for model 1 a local size of around 23,000 grid points per node is required, WRF shows good scaling on large partitions that would be available on pre-exascale systems, provided the global problem size is sufficiently large.

9. Hybrid parallelization and KNL

For the case of Marconi KNL, WRF can be run in hybrid parallelization mode, where now significantly more OpenMP threads per MPI process need to be allocated. This run therefore should reflect the scalability of WRF when running on novel HPC architectures, which are expected to be equipped with significantly more cores per node. We take a closer look at the OpenMP implementation by performing several scaling runs on Marenostrum and Marconi KNL. While the overall performance on Marconi KNL was not satisfying, we could tune a test case with $V = 64^2 \times 50$ on a single KNL. This was done by varying the number of OpenMP threads. Using 68 threads, we could tune the performance of WRF towards a similar performance as achieved on the

Fig. 9. Strong scaling of WRF-fire (model 3) for $V = 192^2 \times 50$ (crosses) and $V = 384^2 \times 50$ (squares). We show in the left panel the time per integration step and in the right panel the I/O time in seconds.

CPU systems. However, strong scaling of this setup remains poor.

10. Test case 3: WRF-fire

We investigate the strong scaling of the WRF-fire branch (model 3) for two different volumes with $V = 192^2 \times 50$ and $V = 384^2 \times 50$ using Marenstrum 4. The scaling of the time-to-solution of the computational kernel is shown on the left panel of Fig. 9. As shown in the figure, time-to-solution is not further decreased for local volumes around $V_{local} \sim 9,600$. This is around a magnitude larger than the critical local volume for models 1 and 2, which shows that employing different physical models in WRF can drastically change the scaling behavior which can have a large impact on the effectiveness of the software for massively parallel machines

11. Outlook and conclusion: WRF and exascale

In investigating WRF, we found that the computation kernel scales well down to local domain sizes of as small as 700 grid points for the cases of models 1 and 2, and down to 9,600 grid points for the case of model 3. This means that for different models, the scalability of WRF can alter significantly such that a careful choice of the parallelization is mandatory in order to run effectively a given model using large partitions. We found that the time for I/O scales poorly compared to the computational kernels, and constitutes the major bottleneck when scaling on PRACE Tier-0 systems. Moreover, in case of weak scaling, the time for I/O increases proportionally to the global grid size, while the computational kernels scales almost perfectly.

Our findings are that using parallel NetCDF, this I/O bottleneck is mitigated significantly. In the test cases employed, shown in Fig. 10, we found that the percentage of I/O of the total run time can be decreased from 80% to a few percent. Furthermore, we found that for running on systems equipped with Skylake CPUs, a hybrid parallelization approach can further minimize the time for I/O to 1%, while the total time to solution of the computational kernel is not effected.

We investigate the node performance of the computational kernel by running similar test cases on the Haswell partition of SuperMUC and the Skylake partition of Marenstrum 4. The comparison shows that model 1 performs better on Skylake CPUs by around a factor of 1.7 and is optimized for AVX512 instructions. However, for the case of model 2, the comparison between Haswell and Skylake yields similar time-to-solution. In general, this means that the performance of WRF depends strongly on the use cases and the specific computational kernel.

This analysis could be used to propose some strategies in order to use effectively pre-exascale systems. In general, the efficiency of the computational kernel of WRF is maintained as long as the local volume is not smaller than a threshold size. The threshold depends on the computational kernel, e.g. for models 1 and 2 this is found to be $V \sim 700$ while for model 3 this is $V \sim 9,600$. These thresholds should be taken into account, as well as the global physical box size, the resolution, and whether ensemble simulations, which can run in parallel independently, are required.

Another conclusion is that on Skylake architectures, hybrid parallelization should be preferred, i.e. on Marenstrum 4 the run with 8 MPI tasks with 3 OpenMP tasks per MPI task was found to be more efficient compared to using only MPI. Hybrid parallelization enables better I/O performance and scalability on a larger number of nodes. Linking to a parallel I/O library is also mandatory when using a PRACE Tier-0 system. As pointed out, this can reduce the total time for I/O by more than an order of magnitude.

Fig. 10. Percentage of I/O of the total runtime for strong scaling of model 1 with a test size $V = 384^2 \times 50$. We show scaling when using standard NetCDF (crosses), parallel NetCDF (squares), and when using Hybrid Parallelization with parallel NetCDF (stars).

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A Remarks about the compilation

We use different libraries and compilers on the different machines. In this section, will shortly list the used compilers and libraries and point out some important points of the compilation.

WRF and WPS (**WRF P**reprocessing **S**ystem), which preprocesses the input data for WRF, require following additional libraries

- NetCDF
- ZLIB
- LIBPNG
- JASPER

On the used systems most of these libraries were pre-installed and details will be listed below.

A1. Marenostrum 4

For the standard version WRF 4.0, we employ the provided software stack pre-installed on Marenostrum 4. We used following modules:

- netcdf/4.4.1.1
- zlib/1.2.11
- libpng/1.6.29
- jasper/1.900.1

To enable parallel I/O, we additionally compiled *parallel NetCDF*, namely *parallel-netcdf-1.10.0*. Although we compared different versions of Intel compiler, for the final runs we used the *icc (ICC) 18.0.1 20171018* employing *Intel MPI impi/2018.1.163*.

For the compilation we use the configure file provided by WRF, however we slightly change the compiler flags, namely we used

- CFLAGS_LOCAL = -w -O3 -ip -xHost -fp-model fast=2 -no-prec-div -no-prec-sqrt -ftz -no-multibyte-chars -xCORE-AVX512 -mtune=skylake
- LDFLAGS_LOCAL = -ip -xHost -fp-model fast=2 -no-prec-div -no-prec-sqrt -ftz -align all -fno-alias -fno-common -xCORE-AVX512 -mtune=skylake

During compilation, we had major difficulties with compiling the file `module_sf_clm.f90`. The compiler would consume all memory and crash, and we had to reduce the optimization level by changing from `-O3` to `-O0` in the case of `module_sf_clm.f90`. Moreover, to generate the executables several libraries were missing, including `hdf5/netcdf` or `openmp`. The flags and paths had to be added by hand.

A2. Marconi - KNL

For the compilation on Marconi KNL, we use pre-installed software and compilers. We load following packages

- intel/pe-xe-2018-binary
- intelmpi/2018-binary
- szip/2.1-gnu-6.1.0
- zlib/1.2.8-gnu-6.1.0
- hdf5/1.10.4-intelmpi-2018-binary
- netcdf/4.6.1-intelmpi-2018-binary
- netcdf/4.4.4-intelmpi-2018-binary

which led to the Intel compiler *icc (ICC) 18.0.5 20180823*. Due to efficiency issues we also tried different Intel compilers, e.g. *icc (ICC) 17.0.4 20170411*.

For the configuration of WRF we used the option `71`. Additionally, we modified slightly the compiler flags by

- CFLAGS_LOCAL = -w -O3 -ip -xHost -fp-model fast=2 -no-prec-div -no-prec-sqrt -ftz -no-multibyte-chars -xMIC-AVX512 -fma -align -finline-function
- LDFLAGS_LOCAL = -ip -xHost -fp-model fast=2 -no-prec-div -no-prec-sqrt -ftz -align all -fno-alias -fno-common -xMIC-AVX512 -fma -align -finline-function

As in the case of Marenstrum the compiler ran out of memory for the file `module_sf_clm.f90`. Again, we fixed this by lowering the optimization level to `-O0`. Additionally, for the build of the executables, the compiler missed some libraries, e.g. `hdf5` and `netcdf`. They could be added in `configure.WFF` or linked by hand.

A3. SuperMUC - HW

For the compilation on SuperMUC, we used the following pre-installed packages

- intel/17.0
- mpi.ibm/1.4
- netcdf/mpi/4.3

where the version of the Intel compiler is given by *icc (ICC) 17.0.6 20171215*. The module `intel/17.0` additionally loads `mkl.2017.6.256`. Thus we had to compile the package *jasper-1.900.1*. To compile WRF we used following compiler flags:

- CFLAGS_LOCAL = -w -O3 -ip
- LDFLAGS_LOCAL = -ip

B Input - files

In this appendix, we will list the input variables of `namelist.input` which we used for the different models.

B1. Model 1

For model 1, we used different physical schemes given by:

```

&physics
mp_physics           = 10,
progn                = 1,      ! On/Off prognostic cloud droplet number
ra_lw_physics        = 4,      ! long wave radiation scheme
ra_sw_physics        = 4,      ! shortwave radiation scheme
radt                 = 60,     ! (max_dom) minutes between radiation physics calls.
sf_sfclay_physics    = 1,     ! (max_dom) surface layer option
sf_surface_physics   = 2,     ! (max_dom) land-surface option
bl_pbl_physics       = 1,     ! (max_dom) boundary layer option
bldt                 = 0,     ! (max_dom) minutes between boundary layer physics calls
cu_physics           = 5,     ! (max_dom) cumulus parameterization option
cu_diag              = 1,     ! (max dom) additional time-averaged diagnostics from cu physics
cudt                 = 0,     ! minutes between cumulus physics options calls
cugd_avedx           = 1,     ! number of grid boxes over which subsidence is spread,
ishallow             = 0,     ! shallow convection option on/off.
isfflx               = 1,
ifsnow               = 1,
icloud               = 1,
surface_input_source = 1,
num_soil_layers      = 4,
sf_urban_physics     = 0,
mp_zero_out          = 2,
mp_zero_out_thresh   = 1.e-12
maxiens              = 1,
maxens                = 3,
maxens2              = 3,
maxens3              = 16,
ensdim               = 144,
cu_rad_feedback      = .true.,

```

B2. Model 2

For Model 2 we used a different physical scheme and additional modules from the chemical branch. The parameters of the physical model are given by:

```

&physics
mp_physics           = 4,
progn                = 0,      ! On/Off prognostic cloud droplet number
ra_lw_physics        = 1,      ! long wave radiation scheme
ra_sw_physics        = 2,      ! shortwave radiation scheme
radt                 = 60,     ! (max_dom) minutes between radiation physics calls. Recommend 1 min/km of dx
sf_sfclay_physics    = 1,     ! (max_dom) surface layer option
sf_surface_physics   = 2,     ! (max_dom) land-surface option
bl_pbl_physics       = 1,     ! (max_dom) boundary layer option
bldt                 = 0,     ! (max_dom) minutes between boundary layer physics calls (0: call every time-step)
cu_physics           = 5,     ! (max_dom) cumulus parameterization option
cu_diag              = 1,     ! (max dom) additional time-averaged diagnostics from cu physics (only with 3, 5, 93)
cudt                 = 0,     ! minutes between cumulus physics options calls (0: call every time step) **
cugd_avedx           = 1,     ! number of grid boxes over which subsidence is spread, default =1, 3 for dx;5km
ishallow             = 0,     ! shallow convection option on/off. works with cu_physics = 5
isfflx               = 1,
ifsnow               = 1,
icloud               = 1,
surface_input_source = 1,
num_soil_layers      = 4,
sf_urban_physics     = 0,
mp_zero_out          = 2,
mp_zero_out_thresh   = 1.e-12 ,
maxiens              = 1,
maxens                = 3,
maxens2              = 3,
maxens3              = 16,
ensdim               = 144,
cu_rad_feedback      = .true.,

```

The parameters of the chemical model are give by:

```

&chem
kemit           = 1,      ! number of vertical levels in the emissions input data file
chem_opt        = 0,
bioemdt         = 0,      ! update time interval used by biogenic emissions in minutes
photdt          = 0,      ! "-" by photolysis routine in minutes
chemdt          = 8,      ! "-" by chemistry
io_style_emissions = 0,    ! 0: no emissions data read
emiss_opt       = 0,      ! anthropogenic emissions
emiss_opt_vol   = 0,
emiss_ash_hgt   = 20000.,
chem_in_opt     = 0,      ! 0: uses idealized profile to initialize chemistry
phot_opt        = 2,      ! photolysis option
gas_drydep_opt  = 0,
aer_drydep_opt  = 1,
bio_emiss_opt   = 0,
aircraft_emiss_opt = 0,
ne_area         = 200,    ! must be larger than the number of chemical species
depo_fact       = 0.25,
dust_opt        = 10,
dmsemis_opt     = 0,
seas_opt        = 2,
gas_bc_opt      = 1,
gas_ic_opt      = 1,
aer_bc_opt      = 1,
aer_ic_opt      = 1,
gaschem_onoff   = 1,
aerchem_onoff   = 1,
wetscav_onoff   = 0,
cldchem_onoff   = 0,
vertmix_onoff   = 1,
chem_conv_tr     = 1,      ! on/off, subgrid convective transport
conv_tr_wetscav = 1,      ! on/off, subgrid convective wet scavenging
conv_tr_aqchem   = 1,      ! on/off, subgrid convective aqueous chemistry
biomass_burn_opt = 0,
plumerisefire_frq = 30,
have_bcs_chem    = .false.,
aer_ra_feedback = 0,      ! on/off, feedback from aerosols to the radiation schemes
aer_op_opt       = 1,      ! aerosol optical properties calculation (5 options - approximations)
opt_pars_out     = 0,      ! 1: include optical properties in output
diagnostic_chem  = 0,

```

B3. Model 3

We analyzed the fire-branch of WRF which we denote with model 3. The parameters are provided by a test case and are as listed below:

```
&physics
mp_physics      = 0,
ra_lw_physics   = 0,
ra_sw_physics   = 0,
radt            = 30,
sf_sfclay_physics = 0,
sf_surface_physics = 0,
bl_pbl_physics  = 0,
bldt           = 0,
cu_physics      = 0,
cudt           = 0,
isfflx         = 1,
ifsnow         = 0,
icloud         = 0,
mp_zero_out    = 0,
```

The fire parameters are given by:

```
&fire
ifire           = 2,      ! be sure to set sr_x,sr_y in domains-namelist (to set refinement in x,y)
fire_fuel_read  = 0,      ! integer, = 0: no fire, 2=turn on fire model
fire_fuel_cat   = 1,      ! integer, -1: from WPS, 0= use fire_fuel_cat, 1= by altitude
! ignition
fire_num_ignitions = 1,  ! integer, only the first fire_num_ignition used, up to 5 allowed
fire_ignition_ros1 = 0.05, ! rate of spread during ignition, m/s
fire_ignition_start_x1 = 2000., ! start points of ignition lines, in m from lower left corner
fire_ignition_start_y1 = 2000., ! start points of ignition lines, in m from lower left corner
fire_ignition_end_x1   = 2000., ! end points of ignition lines, in m from lower left corner
fire_ignition_end_y1   = 3000., ! end points of ignition lines, in m from lower left corner
fire_ignition_radius1  = 80.,   ! all within this radius will ignite, i fire mesh step
fire_ignition_start_time1 = 120., ! sec for ignition from the start
fire_ignition_end_time1  = 145., ! sec for ignition from the start
fire_ignition_ros2      = 0.05, ! rate of spread during ignition, m/s
fire_ignition_start_x2  = 2000., ! start points of ignition lines, in m from lower left corner
fire_ignition_start_y2  = 500.,  ! start points of ignition lines, in m from lower left corner
fire_ignition_end_x2    = 2000., ! end points of ignition lines, in m from lower left corner
fire_ignition_end_y2    = 1900., ! end points of ignition lines, in m from lower left corner
fire_ignition_radius2   = 18.,   ! all within this radius will ignite, i fire mesh step
fire_ignition_start_time2 = 3.,   ! sec for ignition from the start ! end ignition for sfire
fire_ignition_end_time2  = 503.,  ! sec for ignition from the start! end ignition for sfire
fire_wind_height        = 1.,    ! height to interpolate winds to for calculating fire spread rate
```